

Ocean temperature variation across the Cambrian Botoman–Toyonian extinction event

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Text S1. Additional information of the sections examined in this study

1. Aijiahe Section

The Aijiahe section (N 30°44'55", E 111°03'58") is located near Aijiahe village, about 25 km north-west of Yichang City in the Three Gorges area of western Hubei. This section is well-exposed and consists of the Yanjiahe, Shuijingtuo, Shipai and Tianheban formations (Figure S1). The Yanjiahe Formation is composed by grey or light grey limestone, and yields abundant protoconodonts (indicating a Fortunian age), while the unconformably overlying Shuijingtuo Formation is composed of black shale and thin limestone layers, with the acrotretid brachiopod *Eohadrotreta zhenbaensis*, the eodiscoid trilobite *Tsunyiidiscus actus* and hyoliths being the most abundant faunal components. Associated fossils include brachiopods, archaeocyaths, molluscs, bradoriids, chancelloriid sclerites and sponge spicules (Zhang et al., 2016).

2. Wangjiaping Section

The Wangjiaping section (N 30°48'39", E 111°11'15") is well exposed along the classic mountain road, located on the north bank of the Yangtze River, about 15 km northeast of the Aijiahe section in the Three Gorges area. This section consists of, in ascending order, the Shuijingtuo, Shipai and Tianheban formations (Figure S1). The Cambrian Shuijingtuo Formation consists of black shale interbedded with argillaceous limestone. The eodiscoid trilobite *Tsunyiidiscus actus* is common and occurs dense assemblages on slabs of black shale. Thin beds of argillaceous limestone yields numerous, small, shelly brachiopods (*Palaeobolus liantuoensis*, *Eohadrotreta zhenbaensis*). The Shuijingtuo Formation is overlain by thin-bedded siltstone interbedded with thin limestones of the Shipai Formation with abundant brachiopods and trilobites (Yang and Zhang, 2016; Zhang et al., 2016).

3. Xiaoyangba Section

Outcrops of the Xihaoping Member of the Dengying Formation and the overlying Shuijingtuo Formation are well exposed along a road cut and river bank in the Xiaoyangba section (N 32°29'28", E 107°7'10"), located at Xiaoyang village, 10 km northeast of Zhenba County, south-eastern Shaanxi. The Xihaoping Member is 8.4 m thick and consists of intercalated dark grey bioclastic limestones and silty dolostones. It is unconformably overlain by 116 m of silty limestones and siltstones belonging to the Shuijingtuo Formation. The oldest trilobite-brachiopod association (*Parabadiella-Eoobolus*) from South China was recently discovered from the Xihaoping Member, and indicates an early Age 3. The trilobite *Hubeidiscus*, lingulid brachiopods (*Eohadrotreta*, *Palaeobolus*, *Lingulellotreta*), molluscs and hyoliths, all occur in the lower Shuijingtuo Formation, and indicate a late Age 3 to early Age 4 (Zhang et al., 2021).

4. Yangjiagou Section

The Yangjiagou section (N 33°0'8.3", E 107°54'31.8") is located in Xixiang county, southern Shanxi province, South China. This section is composed of, in ascending order, the Ediacaran-age Dengying Formation, and the Cambrian Guojiaba, Xiannüdong, Yanwangbian and Kongmingdong formations. The basal Xiannüdong Formation yields brachiopods, tomotiids and trilobite (*Malungia laevigata* and *Yiliangella*), which indicate an age in the middle to late Age 3 (Yang et al., 2018), while the basal of the Yanwangbian formation yields the trilobite *Palaeolenus* which suggests early Age 4 (Yang et al., 2018).

5. Xiachazhuang Section

The Xiachazhuang section is exposed on the southern flank of the Huangling anticline (Liu et al., 2017). This section is located about 30 km to the west of Yichang city, 10 km to the south of the Three Gorges Dam. The Cambrian strata consist in ascending order of the Yanjiahe, Shuijingtuo, Shipai, Tianheban and Shilongdong formations (Figure S1). The location has been previously studied, especially the well-preserved, Burgess Shale like Shipai fauna (Liu et al., 2017).

6. Wuhe Section

The Wuhe section (N 26°46'49", E 108°25'36") is located along the Qingshuijiang River, close to the Wuhe village, Jianhe County, eastern Guizhou Province, South China. This section is about 1 km away from the Wuliu-Zengjiayan section, which is the Global Standard Stratotype Section and Point (GSSP) for the base of the Miaolingian Series and Wuliuan Stage (Zhao et al., 2019). The investigated interval is composed of, in ascending order, the Qingxudong, Kaili and Jialao formations. Carbonates are developed at the top part of the Kaili Formation, and several samples yielded brachiopods.

7. Wangcun Section

The Wangcun section (N 28°44'6", E 109°58'8") is well exposed along an abandoned, provincial road on the north bank of the Yongshui River, about 4 km to the southeast of Wangcun town, Hunan Province (Li et al., 2020). The Cambrian strata at Wangcun are subdivided into the Qingxudong (also known as Tsinghsutung), Aoxi and Huaqiao formations. The Qingxudong Formation mostly consists of dolostone, while the Aoxi Formation is mainly composed of interbedded limestone, dolostone and black shale. This section is the para-stratotype section of the Luoyixi section (located on the other side of the river), which is the Global Standard Stratotype Section and Point (GSSP) for the base of the Guzhangian Stage (Peng et al., 2009).

Figure S1. Stratigraphic correlation, samples sites, and important fossil ranges of studied sections.

Table S1.

Oxygen isotope data of both biogenic (inarticulate brachiopods, tomotiids) phosphate.

Sections/ Formations		fossil type	Rock Sample	Test no.	$\delta^{18}\text{O}$ (‰ VSMOW)	1 std.dev.	n
Aijihe	Shipai Fm.	Brachiopods (<i>Eohadrotreta</i> + <i>Spinobolus</i>)	AJH II-1	AJH II-1	12.90	0.13	3
	Shuijingtuo Fm.	Brachiopods (<i>Eohadrotreta</i> , <i>Spinobolus</i> , <i>Eoobolus</i>)	AJH SJT9	AJH SJT9	14.60	0.03	3
		Brachiopods (<i>Eohadrotreta</i> , <i>Spinobolus</i> , <i>Eoobolus</i>)	AJH SJT8	AJH SJT8	14.76	0.18	3
		Brachiopods (<i>Eohadrotreta</i> , <i>Spinobolus</i> , <i>Eoobolus</i>)	S05	Q-10	13.63	0.08	3
		<i>Spinobolus</i>	S05	AJH-1	14.77	0.17	3
<i>Eoobolus</i>	S05	AJH-2	13.86	0.07	3		
Xiachazhuang	Shipai Fm.	Brachiopods (<i>Eohadrotreta</i> , <i>Spinobolus</i> , <i>Eoobolus</i>)	QJP6-1	Q-03	13.08	0.08	3
	Shuijingtuo Fm.	Brachiopods (<i>Eohadrotreta</i> , <i>Spinobolus</i> , <i>Eoobolus</i>)	QJP-SJT-18	QJP-SJT-18	13.80	0.11	3
		Brachiopods (<i>Eohadrotreta</i> , <i>Spinobolus</i> , <i>Eoobolus</i>)	QJP-SJT-17	QJP-SJT-17	14.20	0.24	3
		Brachiopods (<i>Eohadrotreta</i> , <i>Spinobolus</i> , <i>Eoobolus</i>)	QJP-1-3	QJP-1-3	13.80	0.14	3
		Brachiopods (<i>Eohadrotreta</i> , <i>Spinobolus</i> , <i>Eoobolus</i>)	QJP-1-2	QJP-1-2	14.70	0.20	3
		Brachiopods (<i>Eohadrotreta</i> , <i>Spinobolus</i> , <i>Eoobolus</i>)	QJP-SJT-16	QJP-SJT-16	14.00	0.08	3
		Brachiopods (<i>Eohadrotreta</i> , <i>Spinobolus</i> , <i>Eoobolus</i>)	QJP-SJT-15	QJP-SJT-15	15.10	0.09	3
		Brachiopods (<i>Eohadrotreta</i> , <i>Spinobolus</i> , <i>Eoobolus</i>)	QJP-SJT-14	QJP-SJT-14	15.10	0.08	3
		Brachiopods (<i>Eohadrotreta</i> , <i>Spinobolus</i> , <i>Eoobolus</i>)	QJP-SJT-13	QJP-SJT-13	14.80	0.20	3
		Brachiopods (<i>Eohadrotreta</i> , <i>Spinobolus</i> , <i>Eoobolus</i>)	QJP-SJT-12	QJP-SJT-12	15.40	0.11	3
		Brachiopods (<i>Eohadrotreta</i> , <i>Spinobolus</i> , <i>Eoobolus</i>)	QJP-SJT-11	QJP-SJT-11	13.50	0.12	3
		Brachiopods (<i>Eohadrotreta</i> , <i>Spinobolus</i> , <i>Eoobolus</i>)	QJP-SJT-9	QJP-SJT-9	15.10	0.10	3
		Brachiopods (<i>Eohadrotreta</i> , <i>Spinobolus</i> , <i>Eoobolus</i>)	QJP-SJT-7	QJP-SJT-7	15.10	0.18	3
		Brachiopods (<i>Eohadrotreta</i> , <i>Spinobolus</i> , <i>Eoobolus</i>)	QJP-SJT-3	QJP-SJT-3	14.90	0.07	3
Brachiopods (<i>Eohadrotreta</i> , <i>Spinobolus</i> , <i>Eoobolus</i>)	QJP-1	Q-13	13.62	0.15	3		
Wangjiaping	Shipai Fm.	Brachiopods (<i>Eohadrotreta</i> + <i>Spinobolus</i>)	WJP-SP-14	WJP-SP-14	12.56	0.24	3
	Shuijingtuo Fm.	Brachiopods (<i>Eohadrotreta</i> , <i>Spinobolus</i> , <i>Eoobolus</i>)	WJP-SJT2-1	WJP-SJT2-1	13.19	0.18	3
		Brachiopods (<i>Eohadrotreta</i> , <i>Spinobolus</i> , <i>Eoobolus</i>)	WJP-SJT2-3	WJP-SJT2-3	14.55	0.30	3
		Brachiopods (<i>Eohadrotreta</i> , <i>Spinobolus</i> , <i>Eoobolus</i>)	WJP-SJT2-5	WJP-SJT2-5	14.57	0.14	3
		Brachiopods (<i>Eohadrotreta</i> , <i>Spinobolus</i> , <i>Eoobolus</i>)	WJP-11	Q-07	14.61	0.22	3
		Brachiopods (<i>Eohadrotreta</i> , <i>Spinobolus</i> , <i>Eoobolus</i>)	WJP-11	WJP-11	14.84	0.28	3
		<i>Eohadrotreta</i>	WJP-SJT-7	WJP-4	15.24	0.14	3
		<i>Spinobolus</i>	WJP-SJT-7	WJP-3	14.54	0.08	3
		<i>Eohadrotreta</i>	WJP-SJT-6	WJP-2	14.70	0.15	3
		<i>Spinobolus</i>	WJP-SJT-6	WJP-1	14.89	0.09	3
		Brachiopods (<i>Eohadrotreta</i> , <i>Spinobolus</i>)	WJP-SJT-6	WJP-SJT-6	14.89	0.22	3
Brachiopods (<i>Eohadrotreta</i> , <i>Spinobolus</i>)	WJP-6	WJP-6	15.09	0.16	3		
Yangjiagou	Xiannüdong Fm.	Tomotioid (<i>Kelanella</i>)	YJGA21	YJGA21	14.64	0.19	3
		Brachiopods (<i>Eohadrotreta</i>)	YJGA20	YJGA20-2	14.00	0.13	3
		Tomotioid (<i>Kelanella</i>)	YJGA20	YJGA20-1	13.67	0.12	3
		Tomotioid (<i>Kelanella</i>)	Basal-XND	Q-15	13.98	0.08	3
Wuhe	Kaili Fm.	Brachiopods (<i>Hadrotreta</i>)	JH-KL-13	JH-KL-13	13.59	0.06	3
		Brachiopods (<i>Hadrotreta</i>)	JH-KL-12	JH-KL-12	14.06	0.06	3
		Brachiopods (<i>Hadrotreta</i>)	JH-KL-7	JH-KL-7	13.87	0.09	3
		Brachiopods (<i>Hadrotreta</i>)	JH-KL-4	JH-KL-4	14.32	0.20	2
Xiaoyangba	Shuijingtuo Fm.	<i>Palaeobolus</i>	S7-2	XYB-7	14.27	0.18	3
		<i>Eoobolus</i>	S5-1	XYB-6	13.99	0.07	3
		Acrothelidae	S5-1	XYB-5	14.85	0.16	3
		<i>Eoobolus</i>	S4-3	XYB-3	14.41	0.27	3
	Xihaoping Fm.	<i>Eoobolus</i>	S3	XYB-4	13.89	0.16	3
		Brachiopods (<i>Eoobolus</i>)	S2-1	XYB-2	14.09	0.01	3
Brachiopods (<i>Eoobolus</i>)	S1	XYB-1	13.88	0.07	3		
Wan guncun	Aoxi Fm.	Brachiopods (<i>Hadrotreta</i>)	LYX23+7	LYX23+7	13.37	0.16	3

		Brachiopods (<i>Hadrotreta</i>)	LYX23	LYX23	13.36	0.08	3
Note: some rock samples yield more than one genus and very abundant, and thus there were enough materials for testing separated by genus, such as brachiopods <i>Spinoobulus</i> and <i>Eoobulus</i> from rock sample So5, Aijiahe section.							

Table S2.

Measurements of the international standard phosphate NBS 120c.

Standards	$\delta^{18}\text{O}$ (‰ VSMOW)	1 std.dev.	n
NBS 120c	21.77	0.09	3
NBS 120c	21.64	0.04	3
NBS 120c	21.71	0.05	3
NBS 120c	21.70	0.08	3
NBS 120c	21.64	0.07	3
NBS 120c	21.77	0.11	3
NBS 120c	21.71	0.18	3
NBS 120c	21.69	0.17	3
NBS 120c	21.85	0.12	3
NBS 120c	21.77	0.03	3
NBS 120c	21.61	0.15	3
NBS 120c	21.51	0.17	3
NBS 120c	21.54	0.05	3
Avg.:21.69 1 std.dev.: 0.10			

Table S3.

Carbonate carbon and oxygen isotope data.

Sample No.	Average $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ (‰ VPDB)	Average $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ (‰ VPDB)	Position (m)	Sample No.	Average $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ (‰ VPDB)	Average $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ (‰ VPDB)	Position (m)
Xiachazhuang Section							
QJPA-1	-3.4	-7.6	0.5	QJP ₄ (Unit ₄)	-3.59	-12.36	180
QJPA-2	-1.3	-8.3	1	QJP-A	-0.12	-11.50	320
QJPA-3	-3.6	-10.0	5	QJP-D	0.56	-10.64	322
QJPA-4	-6.2	-9.2	10	QJP-E	0.78	-10.20	335
QJPA-5	-2.6	-9.8	15	QJP-E ₂	0.32	-10.87	337
QJPA-6	1.4	-9.0	18	QJP-F	0.00	-9.53	352
QJPA-7	0.6	-9.5	23	QJP-G	-0.06	-9.47	374
QJPA-8	1.0	-9.8	25	QJP-H	0.31	-10.27	380
QJPA-9	1.2	-9.5	28	QJP-I	0.28	-9.64	385
QJPA-10	1.1	-9.7	32	SC ₁ -1	0.24	-10.33	387
QJPA-11	1.8	-9.4	35	SC ₁ -3	-0.33	-10.12	389
QJPA-12	1.9	-9.8	38	SC ₁ -5	-0.59	-10.07	391
QJPA-13	1.4	-9.5	42	SC ₂ -1	-1.00	-9.33	397
QJPA-14	1.9	-10.4	44	SC ₃ -1	-0.34	-10.41	399
QJPA-15	2.1	-10.7	47	SC ₃ -3	-0.57	-11.26	401
QJPA-16	0.7	-9.2	53	SC ₃ -5	-0.16	-10.10	403
QJPA-17	0.7	-9.3	59	SC ₃ -7	0.11	-9.86	410
QJP-SJT-1	0.90	-9.91	0	SC ₄ -1	0.48	-10.17	420
QJP-SJT-3	0.89	-9.55	2.5	SC ₄ -3	-0.31	-8.31	428
QJP-SJT-5	0.78	-10.20	13.5	SC ₅ -1	1.46	-7.84	430
QJP-SJT-7	1.67	-9.77	16.5	SC ₅ -3	-0.25	-8.96	436
QJP-SJT-9	1.92	-8.88	22	SC ₅ -5	-0.10	-9.18	450
QJP-SJT-11	1.41	-9.90	31	SC ₅ -7	-0.62	-9.69	458
QJP-SJT-13	1.37	-9.39	42	SC ₅ -9	-0.25	-9.41	474
QJP-SJT-15	1.11	-9.71	50				
Wangjiaping Section							
WJPSJT2-5	1.38	-8.67	31	WJPSJT2-1	2.50	-8.54	37
WJPSJT2-4	2.13	-11.51	33	WJPSJT2-2	1.84	-6.79	39
WJPSJT2-3	1.91	-6.50	34.5	WJPSJT2-6	2.47	-9.82	50
Yangjiagou Section							
YJGA-10	-0.21	-8.77	44.5	YJGA-32	0.22	-8.27	212
YJGA-11	-0.75	-9.86	87.2	YJGA-33	0.16	-7.81	219
YJGA-12	-1.31	-10.01	92.8	YJGA-34	0.38	-7.69	226
YJGA-13	-0.93	-9.86	96.5	YJGA-35	0.39	-7.78	233
YJGA-14	0.63	-9.42	98.4	YJGA-36	0.60	-7.61	240
YJGA-15	0.21	-9.03	103.3	YJGA-37	0.38	-7.83	278
YJGA-16	-2.35	-9.96	107.7	YJGA-29	0.06	-8.29	285
YJGA-17	-2.89	-9.79	116.3	YJGA-28	-1.89	-8.87	292
YJGA-18	-2.28	-9.89	121.9	YJGA-27	-2.31	-7.80	312
YJGA-19	-1.52	-9.66	154.16	YJGA-26	0.66	-7.00	332
YJGA-20	-1.03	-8.15	190.1	YJGA-25	1.24	-7.32	352
YJGA-21	-0.05	-9.65	191.3	YJGA-24	-1.60	-7.29	382
YJGA-30	-1.21	-7.99	198.3	YJGA-23	-2.66	-7.65	402
YJGA-31	0.69	-6.84	205	YJGA-22	-1.17	-6.96	423
Wuhe Section							
JHKL-1	-0.31	-9.88	0	JHKL-7	0.00	-8.75	19
JHKL-2	-0.24	-9.80	2	JHKL-8	-1.11	-9.05	20
JHKL-3	-1.00	-10.14	4	JHKL-9	-2.52	-10.71	20.5
JHKL-4	-0.12	-9.69	14	JHKL-10	-2.62	-9.99	24.5
JHKL-5	-0.21	-10.52	16	JHKL-11	-1.95	-8.65	26
JHKL-6	-0.72	-9.83	18	JHKL-12	-2.30	-10.93	31.8
Wangcun Section							
LYX-1	0.00	-9.17	2.7	LYX-21	-1.59	-6.20	101.8
LYX-2	0.01	-8.77	8	LYX-22	-3.24	-10.23	103.6

LYX-3	0.17	-9.05	16	LYX-23	-2.46	-10.87	105.5
LYX-4	-0.73	-8.67	35.7	LYX-24	-2.59	-10.09	108.8
LYX-5	0.05	-8.56	49.6	LYX-25	-2.36	-10.19	109.9
LYX-6	-0.37	-9.01	53.3	LYX-26	-1.90	-7.04	111.7
LYX-7	-0.40	-7.04	58.1	LYX-27	-1.99	-8.20	112.6
LYX-8	0.04	-6.14	59.7	LYX-28	-1.91	-11.97	114.2
LYX-9	-0.19	-6.49	62.4	LYX-29	-1.13	-6.48	116.1
LYX-11	-0.23	-5.80	70.4	LYX-30	-0.79	-9.59	119
LYX-12	-0.28	-5.93	75.7	LYX-31	-0.76	-9.00	122.5
LYX-13	-0.50	-5.59	78.9	LYX-32	-0.89	-9.86	124.1
LYX-14	-0.58	-5.24	83	LYX-33	-1.11	-6.22	125.7
LYX-15	-0.98	-7.59	84	LYX-34	-1.56	-9.91	127.1
LYX-19	-1.49	-5.16	91.8	LYX-35	-1.95	-9.92	128.1
LYX-20	-1.58	-5.09	93.5	LYX-36	-0.76	-9.68	130.9